

IMPACT OF CYBER HARASSMENT ON THE SELF-ESTEEM AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF PAKISTANI ADOLESCENTS: IN GENDER PERSPECTIVE

Dr. FOUZIA PARVEEN

Visiting Lecturer, Department of Education, Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan, Punjab, Pakistan.
Email: fouziarizwan99@gmail.com

AISHA KHAN

Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology Women University Multan Punjab, Pakistan.

MAHAM SHAMS

Lecturer, Department of Media and Communication Studies, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur.

QURAT UL AIN SHAMS

Visiting Lecturer, Department of Education, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur.

Dr. IJAZ HUSSAIN

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan.

SOBIA ALTAF

Lecturer, Department of Educational Training, Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan.

MANAM RIZWAN

BS Psychology, Forman Christian College, University, Lahore.

Abstract

Cyber-harassment among secondary and higher secondary (HSSC) Pakistani adolescent's academic achievements and self-esteem in genders perspective, being the main objective of this article, has a lot of potential. Study was designed to quantitatively examine the sample by using stratified sampling technique. **Cyberbullying Victimization Scale (Patchin and Hinduja, 2010)**, was adapted. Descriptive analysis was conducted using version 26 of the Statistical Kit for SPSS (Social Sciences). To explore impact of cyber harassment among students regression analysis was done in order. The T-Test study was conducted to identify the gender variances. The results concluded that a negative significant difference is present among the genders regarding cyber harassment victimization. It showed that the cyber harassment impact on adolescent's self-esteem as well as their academic achievement. Feminine seem to have a stronger opinion than male adolescents, regarding cyber harassment. Therefore, it is very important for educational institutes to hire psychologists to ensure a positive support system for the adolescents. This study contributes to helpful the current and future role of social media in preventing cyber harassment.

Keywords: Cyber Harassment, Adolescents, Self-Esteem, Academic Achievement, Genders Perspectives

INTRODUCTION

As the practice of modern technologies, the usage of social media has been enlarged. It has enhanced the risk of youth being harassed and it appears as a huge concern for parents, teachers, and other working professionals remarkably [1]. Researches showed that 95% of adolescents are connected with internet [2]. Some authorities said Cyber

harassment affected minimum 10% of adolescents of all ages groups across the world [3]. Majority of the people using the social media in Indonesian, china and other countries are growing considerably from year to year [4].

Definitions of cyber harassment fall into two key sessions. Some scholar's views about cyber harassment as a new form of old-style harassment, this conventional definition initially recommended by Olweus, as which circumstances are frequently repetition over time also it involves a power difference between target and perpetrator as an intention to harm. Olweus, also described harassment as an overrated phenomenon that preferring a simply an extension of face to face harassment into the cybernetic world. He contends that cyber harassment low occurrence and most of those who are being cyber harassed are also being bullied in traditional ways in the 'real' world [5]. This entrance of the social media in this state has enlarged with wide-ranging convenience of smart mobile phones and other such web-enabled technologies [6]. A significant quantity of this age assembly is consuming the web for the purpose of social networking. Social-media sites are the utmost prevalent resources of operational communication in Indonesia and other countries of the world [7]. Individuals are now frequently being associated to the online harassment and have contact to social media all time a day, due to advancement in technologies [8]. Topologies have many advantages but just like every other thing, it can be useful as well as harmful. By using Phones cameras, texting, email and adults to bully their peers have used websites, etc. Cyber harassment is also called cyber bullying which is now seen as a global problematic issue [9]. Online intimidation is noticeably defined as presence as a clamorous intentional action or behavior that are conducted out through a solitary or group continually and over time in contradiction of the victims, who can't have defined him or herself [10]. Various significant categories such as relational, physical, and verbal (e.g. social prohibiting) and are not deliberate, such as dispersal of rumors could mention such as 'customary' kind of harassment (bullying). Nowadays online harassment via electric media, specifically mobile phones that is connected with internet has emerged which often labeled as cyber harassment [11].

Cyber Bullying and Self Esteem

For the period of adolescence, persons go through a developing stage where they develop their self-identity. Tease others becomes a part of the society of these individuals. If an act of bullying and taunting others threatens the identity of another adolescent, it may be considered a joke or a criminal offense [12]. This teasing and insulting attitude takes a usage of cyber harassment [13]. With low self-esteem, people frequently report experiencing cyber harassment, which is a perception and victimization [14]. Self-worth also signifies to the one's self-assessment of others social role and also influenced the self-esteem [15]. Previous studies alarmed with low self-esteem that influenced by cyber harassment. In social bonding theory **Travis Hirschi's** argues that individuals who have solid and long-lasting attachments to their society in the form of investments or attachments, involvement, and faith are less likely to differ than individuals who have shallow or bonds [15].

Cyber bullying and academic achievements

The electronic media required more attention in literature due to the dynamic nature and wide spread use [16]. In this work researcher focused cyber harassment and its influence on 9th and 11th secondary class's student's exams grades. As per literature, the students who have been bullied are found to score low on measures of academic achievement.

Due to the wide spread and dynamic use of the electronic broadcasting needs additional attention in literature. The adolescents who have been bullied are originating to low score on the measures of academic achievement [17].

Researchers also indicate adolescence catch a negative impact on academic achievement in their academics due to cyber harassment [18]

The effect of social, verbal, physical, and cyberbullying victimization on academic performance. *Victims & Offenders*, 15(1), 1-21. Consequences are vital because of high-worth education yonder the initial level is important for the well-being of to some extent the country. Several qualitative studies have shown that the sufferers of cyber harassment are not able to concentrate and they feel frightened in attending the class in school [19] stated that cyber harassment in school might negative impact on adolescents' academic achievements. [20] Pointed out that skipping school and academic achievement due to the bullying among the adolescents. According Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2019) every day some adolescents skipped school due to the fear of bullying [21]. (Jungert et al., 2021) also stated that victimization effects academic performance [22]. (Sivabalan et al., 2020) indicated that adolescents who were victim of cyber harassment often struggled with academic achievements in school [23].

Cyber bullying in Gender Perspective

The current prose ruminates of gender differences in standings of bullies and youngsters who suffered cyber harassment. Numerous studies illustrate that at hand are important gender variances; however, few studies illustrate that there are negligible gender variations. In a research no alteration was found as 8.6% of pupils were described as the sufferers of cyber bullying [24]. Some other researches showed male students are more likely tangled in traditional bullying than to female. (Jolliffe & Farrington, 2006), a research on cyber bullying and harassment suggests that gender difference have not continually emerged [25]. Numerous researches did not investigate gender difference between male and female youngsters as a victim or offender, other studies have found female students are more cyber sufferers although there is no gender unpredictability on Being cyber bullied to other [26]. Till now, other studies showed boys are cyber bullies as compared to girls [27]. A foremost gender impact appeared always because females, which might be supplementary, complained in face to face [28,29].

Theoretical Perspective

(Erikson, 1977) development stages and (Bronfenbrenner, 1994) ecological system theory used to support the idea that if adolescents cannot manage conflicts and harassment, their stage of development and overall performance will be harmed. This theory is related to the belief that cyberbullying or cyber harassment. Teenagers between

the ages of 7 and 20 may experience cyberbullying, according to Erickson's Theory. The primary goal of adolescence, according to Erikson (1968), is the development of an individual's identity [30]. During this stage, adolescents go through a variety of physical, cognitive, psychological, and social changes as well as face significant developmental challenges related to autonomy, identity, intimacy, sexuality, and academic performance. Bullying frequently results in the victim assuming the role of a negative identity, which could be seen as self-development as a result of [31].

METHOD OF RESEARCH

The statistics were measured using version 26 of SPSS. The descriptive analysis was used to determine the descriptive properties of the study density. Moreover, Regression analysis was used to explore the effect of harassment on students. T-Test study carried out to calculate gender variance in the research variables. On the other hand, "Pearson Moment Correlation Analysis" has been applied to measure the link between cyber bullying, academic performance and self-esteem. The population is the complete number of substances from which subjects are shortlisted [32]. The participants in this descriptive (cross-sectional) research were 9th and 11th-class adolescents from the public sector of secondary and higher secondary institutes. The sample was the variable of subjects which were chosen from that population. For the grounds of this research, a set of 3600 adolescents from the public schools was chosen randomly for involvement in this study. In this research, the descriptive study slant was used to collect information. The goal of this research was to analyze the impact of cyber harassment on the youth of Pakistan and to analyses the role of cyber harassment on self-esteem and academic achievements. Thus, the researcher described the effect of the individualistic independent variable study components over the dependent research variables.

The gender variables will also be described as attained. Moreover, it studies the pre-existing facts and explains the results neutrally and purposely. This research has applied quantitative ideas to conduct study since it has proved to be found suitable for studying certain homo sapiens behavior [33]. Study design is actually a blueprint of the basic foundation of research.

Zikmund also explained it as, "a master plan analyzing the ways and methods for gathering and sampling a procedure used to approach the people has been stratified by random sampling."

Since then, the research is based on gathering information from Punjab; the complete 9 divisions of the province have been added in the list. An area has been freely chosen from each division. On top of that, the enlisted Government secondary and higher secondary schools of the districts were searched from the internet (through the information regarding the admission officers of districts). A random variable was chosen from an information sheet. The chosen variable was number 1, and from enlisted of secondary and higher secondary schools, each one at number 1 was chosen for both gender participants.

Data Collection:

Cyber Bullying Victimization Scale (Patchin & Hinduja, 2010) was adapted for collecting data the Cronbach's alpha for cyber victimization scale has been around .71.

Self-esteem According to the circumstances "Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg, 1965)". Cronbach's alpha was .88 of this scale. For the purposes of academic achievement grades of students which they score in their exams of last year was estimated. Lower grades in a specific class showed low academic achievement while high grades show high academic attainment.

Tools' Validity and Reliability

The sample's internal consistency and the accuracy of the adopted scales were found by calculating Cronbach's Alpha.

Factor-wise Reliability

Factors	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Cyber harassment	12	.751
Self-Esteem	10	.668

DATA ANALYSIS

Responses of school going Adolescents about Cyber harassment

Items	Mean	SD
❖ How frequently had you develop target of cyber harassment for the period of the last twelve months?	1.99	0.774
❖ Somebody made hatred comments about me on social media networking.	1.90	0.641
❖ Had somebody shared my inappropriate or negative pictures on interacting media?	1.83	0.665
❖ Had somebody shared my inappropriate or negative video on social networking sites?	1.82	0.603
❖ Had somebody generated my fake account on social media?	1.38	0.698
❖ Had somebody posted false story about me on internet?	1.12	0.327
❖ Had somebody tried to bully me by texting on cell phone?	1.34	0.489
❖ Had somebody tried to bully me online that he will harm me?	1.12	0.326
❖ Had somebody make-believe to be online, behaving as disrespectful?	1.87	0.890
Cyber harassment =	1.70	0.246

Above table indicates the average score ($M = 1.70$ and $SD = 2.46$) reveals that school going adolescents are slightly not satisfied with the level of cyberbullying behavior. somebody made hatred comments about me on social media networking. Mean score of this question indicate $M = 1.90$ and $SD = .641$. The responses with lowest mean score is $M = 1.12$ and $SD = 0.326$ somebody threatened to hurt me social media.

Responses of school going Adolescents about their Self Esteem

Items	M	S.D
❖ I feel that I'm a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.	3.13	0.841
❖ At times, I think I am no good at all.	2.71	1.06
❖ I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	2.26	1.03
❖ I am able to do things as well as most other people.	3.10	0.991
❖ I feel I do not have much to be proud of.	2.00	0.873
❖ I certainly feel useless at times.	2.86	0.990
❖ At times, I think I am no good at all.	2.71	1.06
❖ I wish I could have more respect for myself.	1.36	0.640
❖ All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure.	2.29	0.909
❖ I take a positive attitude toward myself.	2.48	0.927
Self Esteem =	2.46	.349

The actual declarations are given in the appendix

The findings describe in above the MS also SD of to each declaration on the self-esteem. The average score $M = 2.46$ and $S.D = 0.349$ school going students revealed that they are agreed and satisfied with the level of self-esteem although, some students do not necessarily agree with the level of self-esteem. The responses with highest M score is $M = 3.10$ and $S.D = 0.916$ is that I am able than others. The responses with lowest M Score $M = 1.36$, $S.D = 0.640$ is that i respect more or myself.

Correlation between factors of cyber harassment victimization and adolescents' academic achievement

Variables	M	S.D	1	2	3	4	5
❖ Cyber harassment	1.70	0.246	0.411**	1	-	-	-
❖ Self-Esteem	2.46	0.349	0.244**	0.622**	0.180**	1	-
❖ Academic Achievement	1.71	0.727	0.055**	0.084**	0.102**	0.026	1

** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. (**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2tailed))

The Correlation between the cyber harassment factor with academic achievement are in above table indicate high correlation $r = 0.026$, $p < 0.01$ and association was high between academic achievement and self-esteem $r = .091$, $p < 0.01$ also.

Gender-wise comparison of Cyber harassment

	Gender						95% CI for M Difference	t	Df
	Male			Female					
	M	S.D	N	M	S.D	N			
Cyber harassment	1.68	.295	1614	1.72	.183	1622	.055, .021	-4.407	26

* $p < .05$.

Above table reveals that there is significant difference be existent between male adolescents' $M = 1.68$, $S.D = 0.295$ and female adolescents' $M = 1.72$, $S.D = 0.183$ with regard to cyber harassment, $t = -4.407$, $p < 0.000$. The high Mean score of female school

going students indicates that their opinion is more strong with cyber harassment as compared to male students.

Gender-wise comparison of Self-Esteem

	Gender						95% CI for M Difference	t	df
	Male			Female					
	M	S.D	N	M	S.D	N			
Self-Esteem	2.56	0.279	1614	2.35	0.381	1622	0.180, .226	17.331	29

* $p < .05$.

Above table shows that there is significant difference be existent between male students (M = 2.56, S.D = 0.279) and female students (M = 2.35, S.D = 0.381) with concern to Self-Esteem, $t = 17.331$, $p < 0.000$. The high Mean score of male adolescents shows that their point of view is more strong as compared to female students with Self-Esteem.

Regression Analysis of cyberbullying and Self-Esteem

Dependent Variable	B	T	F	R ²
Self-Esteem	-0.232	72.238	184.235	0.054

** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ Cyber bullying = Independent Variable

Above table displays the findings of regression Analysis for cyber bullying with self-esteem. Cyber bullying showed a significant contribution ($R^2 = 0.054$, $F = 184.235$, $p < 0.01$). It is evident that one-unit increase in cyber bullying ($\beta = -0.232$, $p < 0.01$) will cause -23.2% increase in students' self-esteem.

Regression Analysis of cyber harassment and students' academic accomplishment

Dependent Variable	B	t	F	R ²
academic accomplishment	0.075	14.902	18.516	0.006

** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. Independent Variable = cyber harassment

Above table reveals that the findings of regression analysis for cyber bullying with students' academic accomplishment. Cyber harassment exhibited a significant impact ($R^2 = 0.006$, $F = 18.516$, $p < 0.01$). It is evident that one-unit increase in cyber harassment ($\beta = 0.075$, $p < 0.01$) will cause 7.5% upsurge in students' accomplishment.

Regression Analysis of self-esteem and academic achievements

Dependent Variable	β	t	F	R ²
Academic accomplishment	0.091	13.754	26.863	0.008

** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. Self-Esteem = independent variable

The results of regression Analysis in above table show a significant impact ($R^2 = 0.008$, $F = 26.863$, $p < 0.01$). It is evident that one-unit increase in self-esteem ($\beta = 0.091$, $p < 0.01$) will cause 9.1% increase in students' academic accomplishment.

DISCUSSION

Cyber harassment in preceding decades has occurred as a phenomenon at the institute levels. MacDonald and Roberts-Pittman (2010) examined experience of cyber bullying in students, researches suggested that cyber harassment is also problematic issue among school going adolescents [34]. In schools, students usually come from different cultures, families, atmospheres. For that reason, at school they originated different factors. There are new peer groups, people from different religions, casts, tribes are there. They used different languages. Students with altered temperaments are also there. The current study was an effort to find out the impact of cyber harassment on school going adolescents' self-esteem and academic achievements in gender perspective.

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of cyber harassment among secondary and higher secondary (HSSC) Pakistani adolescent's self-esteem and academic achievements in genders perspective. The objective of current study was to fill an existing gap in literature related the impact of cyber harassment on adolescents of secondary and higher secondary students. Scale wise explanation through analysis of data is helpful in meeting the first research objective of this research. It revealed that school going adolescents were slightly disagreed with the level of cyber harassment. Study of (Tanrikulu, 2018) support these findings. Majority respondents chosen the options once or twice for the statements 1, 2, 3 that were about posting hurtful comments, harmful picture, harmful videos about them [35].

The results were in line with the results of study conducted by Hunter et al. 2020 that concentrated on adolescents who had experiences of cyber harassment. He indicated that adolescents who are cyber victims were also victim of cyber harassment.

The third objective of the study was to explore the impact of self-esteem and academic achievement on cyber harassment. The results showed that cyber bullying had a significant influence on self-esteem and academic achievement. The study findings are also in the line with (Noipom et al., 2023; Noll, 2016) Patchin and Hinduja (2010) explained that cyber harassment was found to be correlated with lower self-esteem. Through its exclusive focus on the relationship between self-esteem and cyber harassment, this work provides additional evidence that electronic forms of adolescent aggression need the attention of educators and additional youth-serving adults. Practice with cyber bullying, both as a victim and as an offender, was associated with significantly lower levels of self-esteem, even after controlling for demographic [36]. Cyber harassment affected student's academically and emotionally, said by Faryadi (2011). Furthermore, the majority of the respondents were of the view that cyber bullying had an adverse effect on academic achievements of the victims. The results of other study of Yehuda Peled,(2019) indicated that cyber bullying has an influence on the psychological aspects like self-esteem, performance of adolescents'. Author links open overlay panel [36].

He investigated that the impact of cyber harassment is adversely affected on student's academic progress. The last objective of the study was to explore the gender differences among the study variables. Simple t-test analysis was used to measure the gender

differences. The results revealed that female students indicates that their opinion is more strong with cyber harassment as compared to male students, [37] also supported these results. Many students who are victims of cyber bullies suffer silently; they are reluctant to complain to the authorities or their parents owing to the social stigma attached to victims of bullies. As such, parents, teachers and institutional authorities have to be on the lookout for such occurrences [38].

CONCLUSIONS

Based on study findings, following conclusions were drawn.

1. It was concluded that cyber harassment showed a significant influence with self-esteem.
2. Research concludes that there is significant difference existed between male and female with regard to cyber harassment. The high mean score of female students indicates that their opinion is more strong with cyber bullying as compared to male students.
3. Conclusion showed that there is significant difference existed between male and female with regard to Self-Esteem. The high mean score of male students indicates that their opinion is more strong with Self-Esteem as compared to female students.
4. Research concluded that cyber harassment showed a significant influence with students' academic achievement.
5. It was concluded that self-esteem showed a significant influence with students' academic achievement.

The topic impact of harassment among adolescents has increased widespread awareness and attention in recent years. On the bases of study findings;

1. Policymakers ought to back educational institutions by supplying advanced technology and financial resources to sustain their efforts in combating cyber harassment.
2. Schools should create and support environment that protects students from cyber harassment.
3. The Government and Institutes and social media must provide and endorse information technology what to purchase in order to prevent cyber harassment.
4. In Pakistan, bureaucracy should perform their job in the right way. This existing problem at the country level some issues resolve by law and legislation and justice reform.
5. To develop awareness about technology, use and intervention and prevention strategies should also set in this perspective.

References

- 1) Borraccino, A., Marengo, N., Dalmasso, P., Marino, C., Ciardullo, S., Nardone, P., & 2018 HBSC-Italia Group. (2022). Problematic social media use and cyber aggression in Italian adolescents: the remarkable role of social support. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(15), 9763. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/19/15/9763>
- 2) Al Qudah, M. F., Al-Barashdi, H. S., Hassan, E. M. A. H., Albursan, I. S., Heilat, M. Q., Bakhiet, S. F. A., & Al-Khadher, M. A. (2020). Psychological security, psychological loneliness, and age as the predictors of cyber-bullying among university students. *Community mental health journal*, 56, 393-403. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10597-019-00455-z>
- 3) Sanmartín Feijóo, S., Foody, M., O'Higgins Norman, J., Pichel Mira, R., & Rial Boubeta, A. (2021). Cyberbullies, the cyberbullied, and problematic internet use: Some reasonable similarities. *Psicothema*. <https://redined.educacion.gob.es/xmlui/handle/11162/207685>
- 4) Tian, X. (2016). Investigating cyberbullying in social media: The case of Twitter. <https://digitalcommons.kennesaw.edu/ccerp/2016/Student/4/>
- 5) Beckman, L., Hellström, L., & von Kobyletzki, L. (2020). Cyber bullying among children with neurodevelopmental disorders: A systematic review. *Scandinavian journal of psychology*, 61(1), 54-67. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/sjop.12525>
- 6) Rwigema, P. C. (2020). Digital technology and its relevance to political and social economic transformation. Case study of East African Community Region. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 7(4), 1402-1436. <http://www.strategicjournals.com/index.php/journal/article/view/1870>
- 7) Nanda, M. K. (2020). Information Security towards Cyber Security: A Review Paper. *Technology*, 11(12), 156-162. <https://www.bitsight.com/blog/cybersecurity-vs-information-security>
- 8) Mishna, F., Sanders, J. E., McNeil, S., Fearing, G., & Kalenteridis, K. (2020). "If somebody is Different": A critical analysis of parent, teacher and student perspectives on bullying and cyberbullying. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 118, 105366. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0190740920306927>
- 9) Davidson, T., & Bhattacharya, D. (2020). Examining racial bias in an online abuse corpus with structural topic modeling. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.13041*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.13041>
- 10) Kanwal, H., & Jami, H. (2019). Exploring modes, strategies, and psychosocial consequences of cyberbullying perpetration and victimization among university students. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 34(4), 787-817. <https://www.researchgate.net/>
- 11) Okutan, A. (2019). A framework for cybercrime investigation. *Procedia Computer Science*, 158, 287-294. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050919312141>
- 12) Rodzalan, S. A., Arif, H., & Noor, N. N. M. (2021). Formal Generalization of Cyber Bullying: A Review Study. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 3105-3117. <http://annalsofrscb.ro/index.php/journal/article/view/416>
- 13) Park, M. A., Golden, K. J., Vizcaino-Vickers, S., Jidong, D., & Raj, S. (2021). Sociocultural values, attitudes and risk factors associated with adolescent cyberbullying in East Asia: A systematic review. *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 15(1). <https://irep.ntu.ac.uk/id/eprint/42698/>
- 14) Fogleman, N. D., McQuade, J. D., Mehari, K. R., & Becker, S. P. (2021). In-person victimization, cyber victimization, and polyvictimization in relation to internalizing symptoms and self-esteem in

- adolescents with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Child: care, health and development*, 47(6), 805-815. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/cch.12888>
- 15) Li, J. B., Liberska, H., Salcuni, S., & Delvecchio, E. (2019). Aggressive perpetration and victimization among Polish male and female adolescents: The role of attachment to parents and self-control. *Crime & Delinquency*, 65(3), 401-421. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0011128718787472>
 - 16) Wang, Y., McKee, M., Torbica, A., & Stuckler, D. (2019). Systematic literature review on the spread of health-related misinformation on social media. *Social science & medicine*, 240, 112552. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0277953619305465>
 - 17) Torres, C. E., D'Alessio, S. J., & Stolzenberg, L. (2020). The effect of social, verbal, physical, and cyberbullying victimization on academic performance. *Victims & Offenders*, 15(1), 1-21. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15564886.2019.1681571>
 - 18) Livazović, G., & Ham, E. (2019). Cyberbullying and emotional distress in adolescents: the importance of family, peers and school. *Heliyon*, 5(6). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405844019356178>
 - 19) Hsiung, H., Patel, K., Hundal, H., Baccouche, B. M., & Tsao, K. W. (2022). Preventing Substance Abuse in Adolescents: A Review of High-Impact Strategies. *Cureus*, 14(7). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9417217/>
 - 20) Ybarra, M. L., Diener-West, M., & Leaf, P. J. (2007). Examining the overlap in Internet harassment and school bullying: Implications for school intervention. *Journal of Adolescent health*, 41(6), S42-S50. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1054139X07003692>
 - 21) Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2019). Connecting adolescent suicide to the severity of bullying and cyberbullying. *Journal of school violence*, 18(3), 333-346. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15388220.2018.1492417>
 - 22) Longobardi, C., Settanni, M., Lin, S., & Fabris, M. A. (2021). Student–teacher relationship quality and prosocial behaviour: The mediating role of academic achievement and a positive attitude towards school. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 91(2), 547-562. <https://bpspsychub.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/bjep.12378>
 - 23) Mohd Fadhli, S. A., Liew Suet Yan, J., Ab Halim, A. S., Ab Razak, A., & Ab Rahman, A. (2022, May). Finding the link between cyberbullying and suicidal behaviour among adolescents in Peninsular Malaysia. In *Healthcare* (Vol. 10, No. 5, p. 856). MDPI. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9032/10/5/856>
 - 24) Ang, R. P., & Goh, D. H. (2010). Cyberbullying among adolescents: The role of affective and cognitive empathy, and gender. *Child Psychiatry & Human Development*, 41, 387-397. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10578-010-0176-3>
 - 25) Underwood, M. K., & Rosen, L. H. (2010). Gender And Bullying: Moving Beyond Mean Differences to Consider Conceptions of Bullying, Processes by which Bullying Unfolds, and Cyberbullying. *Bullying in North American schools*, 33-42. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/>
 - 26) Guan, S. S. A., & Subrahmanyam, K. (2009). Youth Internet use: risks and opportunities. *Current opinion in Psychiatry*, 22(4), 351-356. <https://journals.lww.com/>
 - 27) Yildiz Durak, H., & Saritepeci, M. (2020). Examination of the relationship between cyberbullying and cyber victimization. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 29, 2905-2915. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10826-020-01768-4>
 - 28) Lazar, L. (2023). The Neural Correlates of Empathy that Predict Prosocial Behavior in Adolescence (Doctoral dissertation, UCLA). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4z8243wk>

- 29) Alshammari, A., Alharbi, M., Alghamdi, A., Alharbi, S. A., Ashfaq, U. A., Tahir ul Qamar, M., ... & Ahmad, S. (2022). Computer-aided multi-epitope vaccine design against *Enterobacter xiangfangensis*. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13), 7723. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/19/13/7723>
- 30) Peker, A. (2015). Analyzing the risk factors predicting the cyberbullying status of secondary school students. *Egitim ve Bilim*, 40(181). <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Adem-Peker/publication/283624064>
- 31) Mukherjee, T. (2022). Performance, Discrimination, and Work–Life Interface: Perspectives in Workplace Health and Well-being. In *Handbook of Health and Well-Being: Challenges, Strategies and Future Trends* (pp. 295-321). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-16-8263-6_13
- 32) Alharbi, M., Alshammari, A., Alasmari, A. F., Alharbi, S. M., Tahir ul Qamar, M., Ullah, A., ... & Khalil, A. A. K. (2022). Designing of a recombinant multi-epitopes based vaccine against *Enterococcus mundtii* using bioinformatics and immunoinformatics approaches. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(6), 3729. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9032/19/6/3729>
- 33) Monette, D. R., Sullivan, T. J., & DeJong, C. R. (2013). *Applied social research: A tool for the human services*. Cengage Learning. <https://books.google.com.pk/books>
- 34) Lin, C. Y., Griffiths, M. D., Pakpour, A. H., Tsai, C. S., & Yen, C. F. (2022). Relationships of familial sexual stigma and family support with internalized homonegativity among lesbian, gay and bisexual individuals: The mediating effect of self-identity disturbance and moderating effect of gender. *BMC public health*, 22(1), 1465. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12889-022-13815-4>
- 35) Tanrikulu, I. (2018). Cyberbullying prevention and intervention programs in schools: A systematic review. *School psychology international*, 39(1), 74-91. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0143034317745721>
- 36) Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2019). Connecting adolescent suicide to the severity of bullying and cyberbullying. *Journal of school violence*, 18(3), 333-346. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15388220.2018.1492417>
- 37) Marín-Cortés, A., & Linne, J. (2021). A typology of cyberbullying in youths. *Revista mexicana de sociología*, 83(2), 331-356. <https://www.scielo.org.mx/scielo.php?pid=S0188-25032021000200331&script>
- 38) Braakman, R. (2021). The effect of cybersecurity messages and personality on cybersecurity behavior (Bachelor's thesis, University of Twente). <http://essay.utwente.nl/87309/>
- 39) van Baak, C., Maher, C. A., Protas, M. E., & Hayes, B. E. (2023). Victims and perpetrators of cyber harassment: The role of power and control and the use of techniques of neutralization. *Deviant Behavior*, 44(5), 690-707. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01639625.2022.2088317>